

The Meaning of the Material: A Survey on the Role of Material in User's Evaluation of a Design Object

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Abstract

Materials, the stuff of design process, have been tools for creating 'value', or otherwise, of what a designer attributes to his final product, since the first ages of man. Obviously, the ranges of 'material' usage in design process have been improved simultaneously with technology and industrial design. However, after a time, they were used for a different aim; which was neither about the function nor about the ease of production. The material of a design became a tool for associating the product with various status; which brought up the issue of the 'meaning' of a material constructed emotionally by the users, by means of both its functional and spiritually created value.

This study focuses on the form and material relationship and emotionally created associations with them by different user groups. Seeing an object produced with a material that is not common can attract attention, but how many people can venture to buy it?

This study examines whether the factors 'gender', 'age' and the 'educational level' make differences on the perception of the material of a design object. The task was applied to 60 people by using groups of objects with different materials: cloth, wood, metal, plastic, ceramic and glass. This study also evaluates the 'approach' of a 'culture' to the 'material' through the exploration of Turkish consumer society.

Keywords: material; industrial design; perception; association

Introduction

One of the most critical parameters in any discussion of design perception is 'material'. Doordan States that (2002), "What something is made of and how the material is employed affects the form, function and the perception of the final design."

It is obvious that, the story of materials, their discovery and subsequent manipulation constitutes a significant thread in the history of civilization and of cultural discourse. In the history, the degree to which humans were able to exploit different materials has been taken as an indication of the level of technological sophistication. The advent of new materials is generally treated as one of the distinctive and determining factors in modern design (Doordan, 2002).

All the improvements obtained together with the technology and the new materials, made the 'material selection' an important parameter of product design (McCardle, 2002, 59). These improvements have also influenced the design education to raise the ability of designers for

making them use the blessings of the technology and different materials in production manners (Rennie et al., 1992).

At first, the ‘molds of material use’ have emerged to adapt just improved technology to the products of design; that is, the frequent use of some materials in same specific areas (such as, glasses in kitchen, or ceramics in bathrooms) made people form common ideas about the ‘materials of design products’. This action was first taken by designers because of the technological limitations, then turned to be a vicious circle; such that, although, in contemporary world, technology allows designers to use all kinds of materials in various objects, it is not easy to ‘change’ consumers’ approaches, ideas or opinions formed beforehand by experience.

This is the point that has been taken as the fundamental subject of this study: form- material-product associations that the people form in time. While shopping or just looking around for spending time, people notice or perceive a product, turn towards it, maybe hold and look closer if possible. At this moment, the material plays a crucial role in attracting people’s attention, but is it really effective on selling it? Seeing an object produced with a material that is not common can attract attention, but how many people can venture to buy it?

The other question of this research is, whether the ‘material perception’ and the ‘material ideas’ of the people are affected by such factors as, *age*, *gender* or *educational level* factors. It is proposed that this information will provide valuable insight for industrial designers into role of the material in consumers’ evaluation of the designed objects.

Purposes of this research

The specific purposes of this study are:

- To understand if people associate some basic geometrical forms with some specific materials (see Task 1).
- To determine whether people think about the keywords such as ‘function’ or ‘production’ while evaluating the material of which an object is made.
- To see if the ‘experience with similar or same object’ affects the overall perception of the product.
- To identify whether demographic factors such as age, gender and educational level have influence on material perception (Task 1 & 2).

Background of the survey

Perception of 'objects' and 'environment'

The approaches towards the perception of 'objects' and the 'environment' constituted a background for the analysis of the perception of materials of design objects. Landauer (1972), in his book "*Psychology: a brief overview*", defines perception as "the receipt and the interpretation of the information about external reality (and to some extent internal reality as well)". The physical world contains much more information than any animal is capable of using (106).

Although all the senses, alone and in combination, play a critical role in determining how we experience the world, most psychological research has focused on 'vision' and 'hearing' - the two sensory modes that are most conspicuous in allowing us to successfully interact with our environment (Feldman, 1992, 86). In the context of this study, material perception is associated with 'visual perception', as 'vision' is the only sense that gives us an extended organized pattern of space and the objects in it (Johnson, 1961,131).

Contemporary psychology is full of divergent, even mutually exclusive approaches, each modeling the perceptual phenomena in fundamentally different ways. Anafarta (1996) defines the most significant ones under four titles in his thesis: Gibsonian approach (ecological), Gestalt approach, constructivist approach and denoted space which concentrates more on the aspects of cultural relativism and signification rather than any mechanical or physiological system.

The titles mentioned above, which were used for the evaluations and the explanations of some consumers' approaches, were examined thoroughly for this research. However, the findings of these examinations were not included in this presentation because of the limitations of available space.

Changing attitudes towards materials through the industrialized society

In 21st century, one of the hallmarks of modern industrialized society is the increasing extravagance in the use of materials. Not only are people consuming materials more rapidly, but also they are using an increasing diversity of materials. Indeed, it has been postulated that

assuming current trends in world production and population growth, the materials requirements for the next decade and a half could equal all the materials use throughout the history up to date (Forester, 1988; 87).

It is obvious that, this surplus in material consumption encouraged 'industrial designers' to use different materials in their 'design products'. From their perspective, the use of new materials in products bestows competitive advantage in many ways; for example, more durable, lighter or stronger materials may provide a functional superiority than the traditional ones. Besides, they may bring about change on 'production facilities'. But, among these criteria, industrial designers consider some indefinable characteristics of materials for the purpose of creating different perceptual values; such as emotions, associations, experiences and cultural differences.

According to Ljungberg and Edwards (2003), the material itself can have a certain metaphysical value. They explain this metaphysical value with different examples. One of them is the villa made of wood. Although they are quite popular in Scandinavia, in Middle Europe such houses are often met with skepticism. The enterprises of the Scandinavian villa producers to export the wooden villas to Germany did not work since German people normally think that wooden houses are inferior and simpler than houses built of stone or concrete. On the other hand, while in Mediterranean countries, wood is perceived more as a luxury material because it is quite rare and therefore an expensive material, in Scandinavian countries, since wood is very common, a house built of stone is typically perceived more expensive and prestigious than a wooden one.

Another example given by them is the kitchen worktops and sinks of different countries. For instance, in a country such as Turkey, kitchen worktops and sinks have traditionally been made of stone (e.g. marble), while in Sweden stainless steel has traditionally been used. The preferences on stainless steel may be correlated with the approaches to the B&O products which are identified as prestigious, expressed to the customers by a unique design and the use of valued materials such as aluminum, which gives a cold and somewhat Nordic feel to the products. With those examples, there is little doubt that the metaphysical values created by the consumers have great impacts on perceiving an object as well as the real cost of the material. (Ljungberg and Edwards, 2003; 11)

So, industrial designers are using those values wittingly or unwittingly. The quality of a product and its material is related with the consumer's experiences and the personal tastes. If a material or a product already exists, then this has an important effect on the decision by the consumer to purchase a new version of the product. In this situation, marketing people tend to give an impression that the older product is somewhat inferior to its replacement (Ljungberg and Edwards, 2003; 11).

This can be considered as an explanation of why plastic has had a poor public image over the years. Because it was originally intended as a cheaper substitute for other materials (Walker, 1989; 102). In other words, it has been seen as standing in for more traditional materials, especially metals. For example, metal containers are acceptable to us through custom. Since it is widely known how a metal container is produced, it can be estimated that metal is resistant to fire and so it is suitable for cooking; but not plastic. A plastic cooking pot contradicts the common understanding of what plastic is and how it performs: one fears that the pot will melt under around the food (Dormer, 1990; 62).

Like Dormer, Soentgen (1997) claims that, people prefer the traditional materials for their every day used objects because they find plastic not linked to the earth. That is; only very few know exactly how it is manufactured. There is no characteristic of plastic, which attests to its relation to earth. The origin of the plastic is not known, whereas everybody can say the origin of wood. Therefore, the more the people know about the material- its origin and manufacturing techniques, the more confident they feel with the help of having control of that material. (49)

For these reasons, plastic has been well suited to its role as a replacement material since its acceptance as a unique material of a design object by the society. For example, the Japanese people appeared to be cheerfully absorbed in the making of imitations with plastic, on the other hand, they have continued to have feelings of distrust and dissatisfaction toward it. (Clemanshaw, 1989; 10)

Similar kinds of attitudes towards different materials have been built up in time. Wood, for example, as a natural material, has been perceived warmer and softer, and associated with characteristic sounds and smells. It has a tradition; that is, it carries associations of craftsmanship. It acquires additional character with time; so, the wooden objects are valued

more highly when they are old. As like wood, ceramics or glass have also long tradition (Greek pottery, Roman glass). They are the materials of great crafts-based industries. Although today ceramic or glass objects are produced by advanced technology, they still carry the fingerprints of older craftsmen, which make them perceived as highly valued traditional materials. (Ashby & Johnson, 2002; 75)

So there is a character hidden in a material even before it has been made into recognizable form- a sort of embedded personality, a shy one, not always visible, easily concealed or disguised, but one that, when appropriately manipulated, can contribute to good design... (Ashby & Johnson, 2002; 75)

As a result, people see, touch, sample and in the end recognize those materials. In other words, they attribute on the basis of their experiences. There are lots of products around which make people create stereotypes and associate some products with specific materials. These associations give the materials cultural weight and solidity. On the other hand, since the ranges of products are boosting every day, the names of materials associated with that products seem to be charged with broader meanings. For this reason, people do no longer make classifications of materials according to their properties and intrinsic cultural meanings. Instead, they use the materials' levels of performance and evocative images generated as integrating parts of manufactured products. (Manzini, 1986; 31)

Seeing an object produced with a material that is not common can attract attention, but how many people can venture to buy it? The next part of this study includes a 'field work' focusing on the form and material relationship and emotionally created associations with them by different user groups. The study examines whether the factors 'gender', 'age' and the 'educational level' make differences on the perception of the material of a design object and evaluates the 'approach' of a 'culture' to the 'material' through the exploration of Turkish consumer society.

Methodology

'Perception performance tests' are used to investigate the people's attitudes, feelings and preferences about the form-material and product-material associations. As it is not easy to

find same objects or forms produced with different materials, the modeling of products and forms have been demonstrated to the subjects from a computer screen.

There were two different *tasks* and each of them was applied to two different 30-person groups. Both of the tasks consisted of groups of objects with the samples of different materials: cloth, wood, metal, plastic, ceramic and glass. After looking all the samples for each object, subjects have been asked to select one of them. Then, they have given three sheets one by one; first one was an open ended question to explain the reasons of choices; second one was a ranking scales sheet to evaluate the factors influence their preferences, and the last one was a checklist for adjectives that affect their choices.

At the 'ranking scale' sheet, the author asked the groups to rank the given factors according to their significance on their choices of materials. The given factors were:

- It seemed more realistic with that material.
- It seemed more beautiful with that material.
- I wanted to make it 'different'.
- I had experienced with that kind of a product made by this material before (or I had seen).
- I thought the environment/place for the usage of that product and this material was the most appropriate one for that environment/place (where?)

And for the last sheet, the given adjectives are:

- | | | | |
|--------------------------------------|-----------------------------------|------------------------------------|-------------------------------------|
| <input type="checkbox"/> transparent | <input type="checkbox"/> domestic | <input type="checkbox"/> durable | <input type="checkbox"/> textural |
| <input type="checkbox"/> brittle | <input type="checkbox"/> classic | <input type="checkbox"/> cheap | <input type="checkbox"/> lovely |
| <input type="checkbox"/> sharp | <input type="checkbox"/> natural | <input type="checkbox"/> expensive | <input type="checkbox"/> light |
| <input type="checkbox"/> cold | <input type="checkbox"/> modern | <input type="checkbox"/> colorful | <input type="checkbox"/> opaque |
| <input type="checkbox"/> reflective | <input type="checkbox"/> tough | <input type="checkbox"/> twistable | <input type="checkbox"/> conductive |
| <input type="checkbox"/> flammable | <input type="checkbox"/> strong | <input type="checkbox"/> shiny | <input type="checkbox"/> heavy |
| <input type="checkbox"/> hot | <input type="checkbox"/> flexible | <input type="checkbox"/> enjoyable | <input type="checkbox"/> clean |

Age, occupation, educational level and gender were all included as demographic variables in the test. The purpose was to apply both tasks to the equal rates of male and female subjects at different ages and educational level. 'Age' factor has been defined in three 10-person groups: 18-30, 30-45 and 45- and over 45. Educational level was also divided into three 10-person groups: primary-secondary schools, high school and university graduates.

TASK - 1: form-material relationship

Three kinds of objects were modeled reflect the basic forms:

Sphere for curved forms, prism for cornered forms and a cone for the combination of both curves and corners (Fig. 1).

By using the 'buttons' on the right of the screen, subjects were asked to try all the buttons to see the models of the objects produced with different materials. For the first task, there were some crucial points that considered as the effective factors on choices:

1. Because the 'size perception' has not been thought as an evaluation criterion, there hasn't been used any 'clue' about size definition of the objects. For instance, there has not been put any other object on the scene or the main objects have never been put on a table.
2. The 'colors' of an object is really an important point in perception matter. Therefore, pastel and mat colors were used not to go beyond the first aim of the test; that is, material perception.
3. The subjects were not been informed about filling in questionnaires for their selections, as it was thought that such information might affect their choices.

For both of two case studies, all the papers of the subjects were examined, evaluated, and there were prepared charts, which demonstrate the results according to the age, gender and educational level differences.

Figure 1, the objects modeled for Task 1

Findings of Task - 1

The ‘total chart’ was prepared to evaluate the overall preferences of people on materials of three objects (Fig.2). For the evaluation of the both two tasks, similar charts were used. The value of ‘y’ axis is determined according the maximum value of a specific section. For example, if, at the ‘*gender-material-form relations*’ chart, for the first object, the maximum 7 out of 30 people had selected a form and the other choices for the other objects were less than 7, the value written on ‘y’ axis becomes ‘7’ for all the ‘*gender-material-form relations*’ charts

Figure 2, ‘total chart’ for the general evaluation of all the choices for task 1
(Cl:cloth, m: metal, g: glass, p: plastic, w: wood, ce: ceramic)

The analysis of the ‘total chart’ indicated that, for all three kinds of forms, the ‘glass’ was the most preferred material, than ‘wood’ comes. On the other hand, the ‘plastic’ was the least selected one overall.

Generally, most of the people try to create a ‘function area’ for even a basic formed object. For example, most of them cannot associate the first object (sphere) with any ‘function’ except from using it as a ‘decorative object’. However, according to them the cornered forms, like the last object (box), are more stable and functional. Therefore, from first object to last, the importance of where the object is used increases gradually.

The appearance of the object, with the keyword of ‘beauty’ is the most crucial factor that affects the choices of people for all of the forms. The other important point is that ‘to make the object look different’ was the least selected choice in ranking questions. Although the unusual materials affected them, when they were asked to select one, their preferences were mostly on the materials that are not common.

Gender-material-form relations:

As it can be followed from the ‘gender charts’ in figure 3, ‘gender’ does not create clear difference between the choices of the materials for all three objects. But, the explanations of the same choices differ depending on the ‘experience’ of males and females, as Johnston

(1998) explains the interpretation of the images with the stored knowledge acquired through learning. For example, for the second object (cone), when the 7 out of 15 men associate the glass cone with a ‘lighting element’, the 4 out of 15 women associate it with a ‘vase’.

Figure 3, ‘gender charts’ for task 1

Age-material-form relations:

There appeared some obvious differences between three ranges of ages. For instance, for the first object (sphere), while no one from first group (age from 18 to 30) selected cloth, from the second and the third group (age from 30 to 45 and the over 45), 7 out of 20 people prefer cloth. (Fig.4)

The second and third group tried to emphasize the function of the first object; for example, three women from these groups defined the cloth ball as a *pincushion* (An object that is used in sewing for collecting sewing needles).

AGE-sphere

cone

box

Figure 4, 'age charts' for task-1.

According to the 4 people out of 10 from first group (18-30), as a decorative form, sphere could be best perceived with 'ceramic'. To them, *ceramic* in a curved form makes someone go towards to the object and increase the desire of touch. A glass sphere was founded familiar from the 'fortune tellers'. So it was evaluated too ordinary to select for the first

group. It is obvious in charts that, the older the subject, the more common materials they prefer.

The second object (cone) was the combination of the curved and the cornered forms. There appeared well-proportioned distributions in three groups especially for 'glass' and 'wood'.

When it is looked to the last chart for the last object, there can be perceived the evident difference between the choices of 'wood' in three groups. While the first and the second groups (18-30 and 30-45) prefer wood (4/10-from first group; 5/10-from second group), there is no one from the last group selected the wooden box. Because, the last object (box) was mostly thought as a 'chest'. For the first group, it could be used as a decorative wooden object that would create an authentic atmosphere. On the other hand, the last group found it quite usual so that it seems cheap. Here is the experience with the material is again an important criteria for the choices.

Education-material-form relations:

As it was defined before, the subjects were divided into three groups as: primary- secondary school, high school and university graduates. Most remarkable difference appeared between first (prim-sec) and the third (university) groups; while time-to-time the preferences of second group approached to both groups (Fig.5).

For example, despite none of the university graduates selected cloth for the first object, in total 7 out of 20 primary-secondary and high school graduates preferred it for the same object. While the third group (university), whose choices were mostly ceramic (4/10), mostly explained their preferences with the form-material relationship, the first group, more than the form, concentrated on the 'function' of the object, and tried to define it.

Figure 5, ‘education level charts’ for task-1

For the second object, there is a balanced distribution between groups’ choices. For some materials such as wood (can be followed from the education-object-2 chart) preferences are equal. Moreover, 5 out of 10 primary-secondary school graduates selected glass for the same object; who were mostly tended to make comparisons between the given forms and the ordinary products used in everyday life. They felt confident when confronted with an usual form. For this reason, they associated the second form mostly with a lighting element, vase or flowerpots; so the choices were between ‘glass’ and ‘wood’.

When the last object is observed, it seems that the university graduates preferred wood (5/10). They found the wooden box ‘easy to produce’ and ‘decorative’. But for the first and the second groups, it looked ‘cheap’ and ‘ordinary’; so they preferred glass or ceramic (5/10; 3/10).

TASK - 2: product-material relationship

Five kinds of products were modeled in computer for Task 2 (Fig.6). This task was applied to a different 30-person group. Again, all products modeled with different materials were offered to the group, and they made the selection. But, only for wooden models, three kinds of wood were included in the Task. Because, for this research, the color, which could affect the choices, is not a specific criteria to evaluate. The important point was that to compare the choices between materials. Therefore, at the graphs w1, w2 and w3 were used instead of three types of wood.

Figure 6, modeled products for task-2

The first product was a container whose function was not clear. Subjects were asked to decide how they would use this product and then select a material for this usage.

The second one was a stool. The purpose was to detect people's preferences when they are faced with a product that can be used both for its 'defined function' (sitting) and its 'arbitrary function' (like using it as a coffee table).

The third one was a set of salt & peppershakers. It was involved in test because of its frequent use as an ordinary object in everywhere. Here the subjects were expected to think on the 'hygiene' criteria, and its prestigious usage on a table.

The fourth one was also included in test as an ordinary product, and a frequently used object for everyone: a pen. But, for members of some groups (for example aged 18-30) 'pen' is used more than the other groups. So, it could be evaluated whether it makes difference or not. The subjects also were expected here to select materials that are not common to keep it as a 'gift'.

The last one was a 'walkman'. It was a technological product as well as it was a well-known one. So, it was chosen to evaluate people's approaches to the materials of the 'technological' products on the basis of the keyword 'production'.

Findings of Task - 2

When figure 7 is analyzed, it is observed that, if the product is a complex one (for example if there is a mechanism in it), people prefer materials like metal or plastic, which are generally used for the production of these objects (like the 'pen' and the 'walkman').

total

Figure 7, 'total chart' for task 2

When it is compared with the first task, the usage of the cloth decreased in task 2 (it was the least selected material for all products). The reasons for that, is the subjects perceived cloth as a 'covered material', and defined it as 'artificial'. As expected, the 'wood' was the most preferred material for product 1 and 2 because of their domestic usage.

Gender-material-product relations:

In most cases, gender differences are observed in choices that indicate 'experiences' and 'expectations'; as it was in task 1. For example, most of the females defined the first product (container) as a piece of 'table ware' and wanted to use it for food protection. Therefore, they selected 'ceramic' or 'glass' as they were hygienic and easy to clean. On the other hand, males preferred to use it as an ashtray or an appetizer (Fig.8).

Figure 8, 'gender charts' for task 2

For the stool, both males and females considered the functional property of the product as expected. They mostly chose wood to use it in their houses. There appeared some unusual materials in both groups, because they thought to use it as a platform or a coffee table.

As it is seen in charts, nearly all of the females evaluated the third product (salt and peppershaker) with the 'hygiene' criteria. For this reason, 12 out of 15 females selected glass or ceramic. Nevertheless, males thought its prestigious usage on the table, and therefore, 8 out of 15 males preferred metal or wood.

For the 'pen', most of the subjects selected 'metal'. People did not only evaluate it as a functional product, but also as a 'gift'. So, some people from both groups selected glass or ceramic, which are not used commonly to produce it.

The analysis of the charts indicates that, the second prominent difference between men and women's choices (first one was in product 3) appears in the last product (walkman). Especially for older women, the 'walkman' was a strange object; that is, they were not accustomed to using it. So, they preferred metal or plastic as commonly used materials for the production of technological objects (8/15-metal, 5/15 plastic). However, some of the men selected glass, ceramic, wood or cloth to make it look different.

Age-material-product relations:

The analysis of the age charts indicates that, over 45 years old people, especially for the technological and the frequently used products, prefer the commonly used materials. For instance, 4 out of 10 people from this group (over 45), selected glass and the rest of them selected ceramic for the third product (salt & peppershakers). For the 'walkman', 6 out of 10 preferred metal, 3 of them preferred plastic and only one person preferred wood (as he associated it with the old radios). They said that this product should be strong and durable (Fig. 9).

Figure 9, 'age charts' for task 2

Generally, the members of the first group (aged from 18 to 30) do not give importance to the 'durability' criteria. Their preferences dispersed equally among all materials; because of their interests in different products produced with different materials.

For product 4 (pen), while most people from the first group (18-30) selected glass or ceramic to make it look enjoyable and different, the last group (over 45) preferred metal for a more prestigious object.

Education level-material-product relations:

As it is seen in figure 10, the education level does not make any obvious difference between the choices of three groups for the first product. It can be said that, the university graduates do not prefer ‘metal’ or ‘cloth’.

Figure 10, ‘educational level charts’ for task 2

For the second product (stool) there appeared a clear difference on the preferences for ‘plastic’. The university graduates (for this product 4 out of 10) believe that, plastic can be

used effectively for most of the products because of its 'lightness' and 'ease of production'. But according to the graduates of primary and secondary schools, the plastic is an unnecessary and a dangerous material. It seems cheap and poor. So, especially for the kitchen products, they never select plastic. To them, ceramic is both healthy and durable. They believe that it is expensive and prestigious.

Conclusion

One of the major findings of this study is that there are some significant associations in people's mind about the form-material and the material-product relations. While evaluating an object, people first try to make a classification, e.g. they force themselves to place this object in a specific category. This categorization mostly depends on the 'functional properties' of the object and it does not make any difference whether it is a usual product or just a geometrical shape.

The most of the participants of task 1 had an opinion about ease of the production of their preferences; that is they knew if it was possible to produce the objects with the selected materials. However, their selections mostly depended on their previous experiences and the desires to use these objects in their houses; as Anafarta explains it (1996), "rather than extracting pure data from the available stimulus, they 'add' information to what they sense to reach a perceptual outcome". For example, while a 'glass box' reminded them an 'aquarium', a 'wooden box' was perceived as a 'chest'. Or, a 'cloth cone' was perceived as a 'lampshade', whereas a wooden one was seen as a 'flowerpot' (see the section on Task 1).

The results of the both tasks indicate that, the people also have some general approaches about the 'material properties'. For instance:

Metal seems cold and icy; it is formal and expensive, so it is not domestic and can be easily used for the production of the technological objects, which should be durable and strong.

On the contrary, *wood* is a hot and a domestic material. It is not too expensive, and some kinds of wooden objects can be used as decorative furniture because they remind the authentic and cultural objects.

Glass is perceived both as an expensive or a cheap material depending on where it is used. But to most of the participants, it is the most ‘dependable’ material among others because of its hygienic qualities and ease of cleaning. Although for small sized products or objects (such as ‘pen’ in task 2) it seems very breakable, for big sized object, it seems ‘strong’ and ‘durable’ (like for box and cone in task 1). This case may also be associated with ‘touch’ and ‘handiness’ factors in perception.

Cloth is mostly perceived as a covering material. It seems domestic but for most of the participants, its texture has a repelling effect on touching.

Actually, it can be said that, *ceramic* is perceived as more expensive and the ‘prestigious’ than the others. It is ‘hygienic’ and easy to clean (such that some housewives said it was much more preferable than glass because it did not show the fingerprints, but “...unfortunately, it is too expensive...”). However, according to them, ‘ceramic’ does not go well with the ‘cornered shapes’ because of its ‘fluidity’ feature.

Finally, *plastic*, for most of the participants, is the most ‘dangerous’ and the ‘cheapest’ one that they did not prefer plastic objects no matter it is used in kitchen or not.

The findings, which were obtained from the analysis of the demographic factors, are summarized below:

1. There is no significant difference between males and females about their associations on forms and products with the materials. But the male participants were seemed more open and curious for new materials. According to Hofstade (1992), these dimensions of genders’ perceptual approaches “ address the fundamental issue of the way a society allocates social roles to the sexes.” (qtd. in Ergeneli & Arıkan, 2002, 257).
2. When it is considered on the basis of the functional properties of the objects, a considerable difference occurs between different age groups. While the older ones (over 45) give more importance to usability of the products, younger ones (ages from 18 to 30) prefer the more ‘enjoyable’ and ‘different’ ones. The effects of ‘trends’ on perceptions are also visible. For instance, today a wooden box can be used as a

decorative object in modern houses but reverse it still seems cheap and old for the older participants who are accustomed to see this product.

3. When the educational level is investigated, it is seen that for the first group's members (primary and secondary schools graduates) the 'durability' and the 'multi-functionality' of an object are more important than their counterparts. However, for the university graduates, because of their life styles (which requires 'rush') the 'lightness' and the 'usability' of the products are much more important than the other criteria. This is the only group who preferred plastic.
4. 'Experience with same or similar product' is another considering factor effecting the perception of materials. For instance, at Task 1, three women at the ages of 30 to 45 defined the cloth ball as a pincushion. A similar approach was observed at Task 2, for the 'walkman' case. The analysis of the charts indicated that, especially for older women, the 'walkman' was a strange object; that is, they were not accustomed to using it. So, they preferred metal or plastic as commonly used materials for the production of technological objects (8/15-metal, 5/15 plastic). However, since the 'men' at same ages (over 45) are more interested with the electronic devices and have more experiences as regards to women, could give more flexible choices for it.

Like many other studies, this research had some limitations. The most important one of them was that there had not been used real objects for the tasks. Because the participants observed the objects from a computer screen, their perceptions about the materials would have been affected by the 'quality of the rendering and modeling'.

Future researches on this subject may focus on the following: first of all it is very important to examine the people's perception criteria on materials when they are confronted with the real product. The studies can evaluate the 'visual perception' of them as well as the effects of the 'textural' feelings. Secondly, the international and the cross-cultural approaches to the perception and the stereotypes can be searched.

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